

Public education and Health consciousness in Bengali proverbs

Sudipta Banerjee, Ph.D. research scholar (IES college of education, IES University, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh)

Abstract:-

[Folk literature is the creation of integrated society. One of the goals of integrated society is the welfare of the collective, its expression in folk literature and culture is noticeable. But it must be remembered that literature is bound to lose its importance where the motive of necessity becomes greater. Folklore adages evolved out of necessity into public health policy. So many people do not want to call health proverbs as literature. But even if they are not considered as literature, it cannot be said that they are completely devoid of literary quality. Moreover, proverbs have become indispensable in the way of life, taking the role of folk teachers. Its reflection is noticeable in proverbs about health. Ancient people were health conscious. They used their life experience for the purpose of social welfare. Proverb is one of those mediums which have been used in the form of folk images over time and have played a role in public welfare.]

Key words:-

Proverbs, Public Awareness ,folk medicine, fruit, herbal medicine,]

Introduction

Folk Education is of the folk (people) for the folk (people) by the folk (folk-culture).

The teacher makes the student a teacher by the knowledge he has acquired along the way in his life. Students of folklore are illiterate working people of rural villages, and teachers are folk poets, folk singers, journeymen. Both teachers and students are illiterate here. But illiterate does not mean uneducated. Reading is not the only way to gain knowledge. It is possible to learn by listening. Writers of folklore are educated by their own folk culture. Life experiences are revealed in their writings. Proverb became the proper medium of folk education. The identity of this diverse education can be captured by citing a few proverbs.

Proverbs are a significant subject of folklore. One of the most important parts of the multifaceted proverb is the proverb about health. Bengali proverbs are the memorable oral traditions that have helped to make people health conscious. Before knowing the nature of health awareness in proverbs, it is necessary to have clear knowledge about proverbs. Many people are not aware of the difference between proverbs and proverbial phrases or catchphrases. Consider them synonymous. But remember, a proverb is a complete sentence, in which the subject, the action and the verb are present. The proverbial phrase is not. These are fractions of proverbs. Many also call them idioms. For example, Naishchaya, Akash-Kusum etc. On the other hand, 'proverb' is the saying of the learned, which later acquired the status of a proverb. For example, poet Bharatchandra's city burns and avoids Devalaya (Temple) etc..

Objectives:-

- To acquire knowledge about the form and characteristics of proverbs
- To understand the importance of proverbs as literary elements of folk culture
- Trying to understand the educational significance of proverbs
- Realizing the need for health awareness proverbs in the society

Methodology:-

It is entirely a qualitative study.

Survey method has been used to collect primary sources as well as various books have been used as secondary source for writing this research paper.

Literature Review :-

Upendranath Bhattacharya's seminal work, "Bangla Prabad," is a comprehensive compilation and analysis of Bengali proverbs. This book serves as a crucial resource for understanding the cultural and linguistic significance of proverbs in Bengali society. Bhattacharya meticulously categorizes and interprets a vast array of proverbs, providing insights into their origins, meanings, and functions. Gopal Chowdhury and Priyanjan Sen have tried to show the versatility of proverbs in their book titled Prabada Bachan. Starting from Dulal Chowdhury, many folklorists have worked on proverbs but only health awareness has been less work on proverbs.

Proverbs, like other branches of folklore, are quite difficult to define. Because a definition is a concise and accurate representation of the subject's characteristics. However, many people have given us the definition of the proverb in different ways. The definitions given by eminent scholars and explanations regarding the origin of the word proverb can be seen:

Gyananendra mohan Das in his 'Bangla bhasar obidhan' of the word 'proverb'

Etymology and explanation says – Proverbs are traditional sayings, popular sayings, popular hearsay, slander, .

Haricaran Banerjee in his book 'Bengiya Shabadkosh' used words such as colloquialism, sambhash, folk slander, tradition, popular folkism, legend, folklore etc.

Proverbs are short, commonly known expressions that convey traditional wisdom, truths, moral lessons, or advice. They are typically passed down through generations and are often used in everyday speech to express shared cultural values and beliefs succinctly.

Basic Characteristics of Proverbs

1. Brevity:-Proverbs are usually concise and to the point, often consisting of just a few words or a short sentence.
2. Wisdom:- They contain practical and philosophical insights, offering guidance or reflections on life.
3. Cultural Significance:-Proverbs reflect the values, norms, and experiences of a particular culture or community.
4. Metaphorical Language:-They often use metaphorical or symbolic language to convey deeper meanings.
5. Rhythm and Rhyme:-Many proverbs have a rhythmic or rhyming structure, making them easier to remember and recite.
6. Aphoristic Nature:-Proverbs are pithy and memorable, encapsulating universal truths or observations in a few words.

7. Didactic Purpose:-They often serve an educational or moral function, teaching lessons or imparting wisdom.

8. Anonymous Origin:- The origins of most proverbs are unknown, and they are considered collective wisdom rather than the work of a single author.

Proverbs play an important role in communication, offering a way to convey complex ideas quickly and effectively through familiar and resonant expressions.

Evaluation of health proverbs in promoting public awareness, public education and public journalism

Health Proverbs describe principles of health care. One of the components of health care is folk medicine and folk medicine. People have traditionally used these material elements for livelihood. At the same time, the advice, warning, and faithful policy of the folk healer have been followed for the protection of health. All these have found a place in the endless store of proverbs. Dr. About the importance of proverbs. Varun kumar Chakraborty try to said: "In the first period of folk literature, more importance was attached to the practice of proverbs. The main reason for this is that the practical importance of proverbs in everyday life is immense compared to other categories belonging to folklore." It goes without saying that health proverbs deserve the lion's share of this importance. In today's scientific age, some rules are considered wrong, but despite the great progress in medical science, the importance of proverbs can still be said to be unimportant. Proverbs have long played an important role in spreading public awareness, public education and public journalism, a role that continues to be effective today.

Folk literature is the creation of integrated society. As proverbs are a major and popular branch of folklore, proverbs are also the creation of cohesive societies. The varied flow of joys and sorrows of the life of the common people of rural Bengal has taken form in folk literature. Lok or Folk refers to the group life in the village of Bengal who carry similar cultural traditions. The individual is sympathetic, responsible and caring towards the traditions of the integrated society, so his work shows the impression of group consciousness instead of the touch of individual talent. Authors of folklore are devoted to society. Bengali proverbs about health ; has been written for the purpose of social welfare and public welfare. Public welfare is possible only by spreading public awareness. Having been popularized and carried over into folk memory for a long time, health proverbs became an important means of raising public awareness for health protection. Proverbs on health are called verbal or folk Ayurveda. In ancient times when there were not so many doctors as nowadays, these tricks were the way to protect people's health. Folklore became particularly helpful in promoting health awareness.

The practice of using various types of folk remedies, health-related restrictions prevailed in proverbs for healthy living. Many times people become the subject of medical advice, warnings etc. And proverbs.

Everything related to social life has a place in the endless store of proverbs in folk society. These include the use of folk remedies for various diseases, various habits for staying healthy, the benefits of eating various vegetables, fruits, etc. What kind of food should be taken, what should or should not be eaten at what time, how to maintain good health—these suggestions are found in proverbs.

Here are some health adages that help raise public awareness and are still effective in today's scientific age.

আলো হাওয়া বধো না/, রোগভোগে মরো না

Do not block light and air; don't get sick and die."

ছোট ছোট কামড়ে/সব ভাতই হামুড়ে

All the rice is chewed in small bites."

বনি খাটুনি খায় ভাত/ শরীরে করে উৎপাত

If eats rice without any effort; Then problems arise in the body"

যার দাঁত সাফ না/ তার আত সাফ না

"He whose teeth are not clean, his heart is not clean."

বড়োও যদি ভোরেরে বলো /থাকবে না আর রোগেরে জ্বালা

. If the fence is early in the morning;There will be no more burning of the disease."

ফল খেয়েযে জল খায় / যম বলে আয় আয়

"Yama who drinks the water after eating the fruit; Yama(God of death) says come come."

নমি-নশিন্দা যথা/মানুষ কঁ মরে তথা।

nim-nishinda yatha/does man die yatha. According to Khanar bachan neem-nishinda tree is beneficial for the environment. In such an environment, people generally live: Diseases are less. So, to stay well, neem-nishinda trees should be planted around the house.

বারো মাসে বারো ফল/না খলে যায় রসাতলা..... খনা

Twelve fruits/uneaten in twelve months is abyss. Khana

In other words, to stay healthy, fruit should be eaten throughout the year. Especially in all seasons everyone should eat some seasonal fruits. But care should be taken that the fruit is free from poison and pure.

খালি পটে জল/ভরা পটে ফল।- খনা

[Water on an empty stomach / Fruit on a full stomach. Khana i.e. water on an empty stomach and fruits on a full stomach are beneficial for health.

ভোরেরে হাওয়া/লাখ টাকার দাওয়া।

[Morning breeze / Claim of lakhs of rupees.

That is, waking up early in the morning and enjoying the fresh morning air (air) is beneficial for health. In many cases it works better than drugs costing lakhs of rupees.

Do not block light/air/die from disease. In other words, playing light and air in the living room is useful for health. It is important to pay attention to this aspect in building houses and planting trees because it is closed that does not get enough light and air.

These health proverbs have helped to keep the folk knowledge related to health fresh in the memory of the people and thus proverbs have become important in creating and increasing public awareness. Health proverbs carried over from folk traditions are helpful in raising public awareness in the field of basic medical treatment even in the present age of science.

Folk medicine is needed to protect public health and folk medicine is needed for that. Dr. About this. Mananjali Bandyopadhyay's comment: "The use of folk medicine in ancient traditional medical management is still alive and relevant today, in terms of modern scientific innovation, it is by no means dead, but it flows from generation to generation, sometimes like Kharsorta River, sometimes like Falgudhara. It is often referred to as an 'alternative medical system' in modern medicine."

Neglected herbal medicine has now gained prominence. Gerbera people suffer from the huge cost and side effects of chemical drugs. People are taking herbal medicine as an alternative. As a result, the demand for herbal medicine is increasing. "All this is possible because the herbal folk lore is fresh in the minds of the people." Proverbs play the role of folk teachers in promoting public welfare by raising public awareness. Dr. Sougat Chatterjee has rightly said, "Proverbs are an important category of folklore. Since proverbs like rhymes, rhymes etc. Are part of folk literature, they also originate from word of mouth. We get many useful lessons for life from proverbs. Proverbs literally take the role of folk teachers in our daily life by giving us the right guidance on what to do and what not to do."

To protect health one should know about hygienic restrictions and use of folk remedies. Some proverbs related to this were mentioned:

Proverbs about ginger :-

আদা সব রোগেরই আধা, or
আদা ওষুধের আধা

"Ginger is half the medicine

Proverbs about Garlic:-

আমার হৃদয়ে বুকো ঘা/ আমারই বললে রসুন খা

"I have a chest wound,/I was told to eat garlic."

পয়াজ রসুন একই গন্ধ, কবো ভালো কবে বা মন্দ

"Onions smell like garlic,/ Some are good and some are bad.

Needless to say, the duties necessary for the protection of health and of course performed have already been mentioned. For example, getting up early, taking a morning walk, taking a bath in the morning. Excretion before meals, eating in moderation, nutritious and easily digestible food, doing necessary work for digestion etc. Besides, we get many other lessons from proverbs that help in maintaining health.

CONCLUSION

Now we will observe how health proverbs play the role of folk-journalism in spreading public awareness and imparting public education. Folk journalism emerged long before the advent of written journalism. That journalism was oral. Folk journalism emerged through folk media. "The main goal of journalism is communication, that is, public relations, spreading the news among the masses and making them aware of a goal." There are two aspects of communication. One action is another reaction in terms of that action. Since folk journalism is not as contemporary as written journalism, it is a time-consuming affair, so its action and reaction are not always understood. But the main feature of journalism i.e. 'public relations' lies in its purpose. Public relations are here between people of their own group and class. Two parallel streams can be observed in the purpose and expression of public journalism, one informal and the other formal. Folkism is caught between two sides. A society integrated by economic, social, cultural and religious ties seeks unity among its members to promote unity of spirit.

Let us give an example of how folk journalism plays an important role in folk culture. In the song 'Gambhira' Shiva is styled as the patron saint of administration. All that has happened throughout the year is served before him. Its real aim is to make the public aware. This is how serious songs or dramas become substitutes for newspapers. Similarly proverbs also play the role of mass media. Many proverbs have been created in Bengal about folk journalism. For example:

খালি পটে পটে জল ভরা পটে ফল

"Water on an empty stomach and Fruits in a full belly".

The restrictions necessary for health protection have been mentioned earlier. These restrictions provide public education through the work of public journalism. People's public consciousness is formed and enhanced by public education formed through public journalism. Thus the public becomes health conscious.

REFERENCE:-

1. Chakraborty, Varun Kumar. "Bangla lokashaito chorchar chorchar", Calcutta, Pustak Bipani, 1986
2. Bandyopadhyay, monanjoli. 'Bangla probad o krishi vigyan' Kolkata Loko Sanskriti o adivasi songaskriti Kendra, 2011
3. Chakraborty, Varun Kumar. 'Loko aushad o lok chikitsa', LokoSanskriti o adivasi Sanskriti Kendra, kolkata, 2004
4. Bhattacharya, Ashutosh. 'Bangla lokashaito ', a Mukherjee and company private limited, Kolkata, 1962
5. Chakraborty, Shyamal. 'doctor Dhakar aage', Ananda publishers, Kolkata, 2012